

International Conference InterGedi2021

**Digital Communication: Identity and
Visibility in Research Dissemination**

Book of Abstracts

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Foreword

Communication of research and dissemination of knowledge is changing and expanding –possibly faster than ever– towards international and digital environments. The increasing demands of this highly competitive scenario situate researchers and their work in a new global, multimodal dimension, where a number of emerging trends can be perceived. Thus, in this glocalized context, the emphasis is laid on:

- international collaboration, leading to a growing participatory culture, but also fostering each scholar's individual role and the need to forge their personal and professional identities;
- a movement towards open science with demands for greater transparency of processes and availability of tools and resources. In this area, the use of social media and multimodal communication has brought about an unprecedented visibility of the researcher and a wider dissemination of results but also the appearance of challenges in the traditional copyright or peer-review systems;
- the reformulation/reconceptualization of scientific research through popularization practices, aimed at a more heterogeneous audience, but often coexisting with the rapid dissemination of vulgarized science or non-validated knowledge through the same channels.

Increasingly, scholars and researchers must acquire and maximize developing professional and discursive practices in relation to these emerging forms of digital communication. This process generally involves a number of adaptations, such as a more active and personal role of the researchers in the process of communication of results, their current aim to reach multiple audiences and the need to master the genres, uses and conventions associated with specific platforms and online environments.

The InterGedi2021 Conference would like to trace and analyse these trends related to the digital communication of science and explore their areas of confluence. More specifically, it is our aim to gather current research on the practices related to the construction of digital identity and visibility, the emerging conflicts related to the public availability and appropriation of scientific culture and the ways of validating and disseminating scientific knowledge in this new context.

We hope you find these papers interesting. Welcome to InterGedi2021.

Ramón Plo, Isabel Corona & Daniel Pascual
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PLENARY LECTURES ABSTRACTS

Dissemination, popularization and vulgarization of science - how to distinguish them?

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These three concepts are distinguished along the axes of complexity of knowledge, level of explanatory ambition, and loyalty to the scientific basis. I will try to distinguish them conceptually and give examples of website communication.

In my view, the democratic ideal would be popularization, which is characterized by an honest attempt of opening the gates between researchers and the 'populus' by attempting to give access to scientific insights and backgrounds for them and making science a part of the popular culture and knowledge. In dissemination, the level of explanatory ambition is lower than in popularization, and in vulgarization entertainment or other non-educational purposes take over, sacrificing the loyalty to the actual underlying scientific results and basis.

About the Plenary Speaker

Jan Engberg is Professor of Knowledge Communication at the Department of German Business Communication, School of Communication and Culture, Aarhus University, Denmark. His main areas of research interest are the study of texts and genres in the academic field, cognitive aspects of domain-specific discourse and the relations between specialised knowledge and text formulation as well as basic aspects of communication in domain-specific settings. His research has been focused upon communication and translation in the field of law as well as other fields of academic communication like climate change communication. He has widely published his investigations in high-quality journals such as *Journal of Pragmatics*, *Ibérica*, *Parallèles* or *International Journal of Legal Discourse*. He is furthermore editor of the international journal *Fachsprache*.

Collaborative Research - An invaluable resource for academic visibility

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Revisiting my extensive experience of an international collaboration (Bhatia, Candlin & Gotti, 2012) across more than twenty countries involving colleagues from a range of disciplinary backgrounds, I would like to illustrate how collaborative research offers a valuable resource that not only contributes to academic visibility, but at the same time, provides opportunities to develop multiperspective and multidimensional frameworks often leading to a more comprehensive and insightful understanding of discursive and professional practices, particularly in the context of the present-day digitally mediated global world enabling speedy communication, consultation, and dissemination of research insights, in addition to encouraging collaborative authorship and opportunities for publication.

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About the Plenary Speaker

Vijay Bhatia retired as Professor from City University of Hong Kong and is now Adjunct Professor at the Chinese University of Hong Kong and Visiting Professor at the Hellenic American University in Athens (Greece). Some of his research projects include *Analyzing Genre-bending in Corporate Disclosure Practices*, and *International Arbitration Practice: A Discourse Analytical Study*, in which he led research teams from more than 20 countries. His research interests include, (Critical) Genre Theory, Analysis of academic and professional discourses, particularly in legal, business, promotional, and new media contexts; ESP and Professional Communication; simplification and easification of legal and other public documents. Three of his monographs on genre analysis, *Analysing Genre: Language Use in Professional Settings* (1993), *Worlds of Written Discourse: A Genre-based View* (2004), and *Critical Genre Analysis: Interdiscursive Performance in Professional Practice* (2017) are widely used in genre theory and practice.

PAPER ABSTRACTS

By alphabetical order

How do winning Three Minute Thesis presenters engage their audience through multimodal resources?

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Abstract

A growing number of universities worldwide are currently holding Three Minute Thesis (3MT) presentations. This genre is defined as a competitive academic spoken presentation that allows PhD students to disseminate their ongoing research to audiences of diverse fields of expertise (Rowley-Jolivet & Carter-Thomas, 2019). This innovative format encourages students to democratize scientific knowledge to effectively explain their research to non-specialized audiences in a maximum of 3 minutes. Previous studies on communication in 3MTs have examined the rhetorical moves (Hu & Liu, 2018), interactional and evaluative positions (Hyland & Zou, 2021) as well as stance and engagement (Qiu & Jiang, 2021) from a purely linguistic perspective at a macro level. However, the role of non-verbal together with verbal resources at a micro level has yet to be explored. This type of multimodal analysis entails detailed exploration of the combined use of modes of communication. Consequently, such a meticulous time-consuming approach can only be done with a small representative dataset unlike the large corpuses used for macro-analyses. In this study, in line with the aforementioned publications, we compare speakers from the hard and social sciences. We analyze how four 3MT 2020 on-line winning competitors engage with the audience by drawing on a variety of semiotic resources. The analysis of the multimodal data was supported by the software ELAN, which permitted annotating the verbal and non-verbal resources presenters used. Results revealed that kinesic and proxemic features, such as gaze and hand-arm movements played an important role in orienting the four 3MT winners' speeches towards their audiences. Thus, it is recommended that doctoral students be trained to develop their multimodal-communicative competence (i.e. ability to understand and construct meaning making use of varied semiotic resources (Royce, 2007)) which will contribute to improving their 3MT presentations.

Keywords

3MT presentations, popularization of science, engagement, multimodal discourse analysis, multimodal communicative competence

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Dissemination of knowledge during the Covid 19 Pandemic: A Conceptual Metaphor Analysis of research and popular articles

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Abstract

Covid 19 has been the focus of different pieces of research throughout the world since the outbreak of the pandemic. Publications about Covid 19 are not only sought by specialists in the field, they are also very much wanted by lay people. As a result, a large number of publications in scientific journals is also accompanied by a wave of popular articles on Covid 19.

Science writing follows norms imposed by the community of practice and one of “key genres used by scientific communities for the dissemination and ratification of knowledge” (Koutsantoni, 2006: 19) is the research article (RA). Disciplines have their “particular norms, nomenclature, bodies of knowledge, sets of conventions and modes of inquiry” (Hyland, 2004: 8). Research on Conceptual Metaphors (CMs) in science writing revealed that they “have a crucial function in the development of models and theories, as well as in the presentation of scientific arguments” (Semino, 2008, 132). Different metaphors have been used to talk about the pandemic like war, fire, enemy, etc. however, “in the move from specialized genres to scientific popularizations and the general media... the same metaphors may be used in a variety of ways for explanatory and persuasive purposes, not just by scientists, but also by journalists...” (Semino, 2008: 145).

The present paper seeks to study CMs in the two genres of RAs and PAs that present medical findings about Covid 19. The purpose is to identify the CMs used in each genre, and the role played by them in each genre. For this purpose, RAs from ScienceDirect and Cambridge on the one hand, and PAs from NewScientist, PopularScience and ScienceDaily, on the other hand, are collected. Both qualitative and quantitative tools (AntConC) are used to extract the metaphorical expressions using the MIPVU procedure (Steen, 2002). The results might reveal how CMs might play different roles in RAs and PAs depending on the communicative purposes of each genre.

Keywords

science dissemination; research articles; popular articles; Conceptual Metaphor; social media

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Predatory journals: A potential threat to the dissemination of validated knowledge in open science

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Abstract

Predatory publishing practices have proliferated in the past years by 25% (Oermann et al., 2018) as a result of researchers' pressure to publish or perish in international journals and, concurrently, the expansion of digital editorial practices and the global trend towards the open dissemination of science. In this context some publishers email flattering paper requests to scholars that offer prompt peer reviews and fast open-access publication. These publishers have been labelled as “predatory”, “illegitimate” or “fake” because they exploit the author-pays model (gold open access) for their own profit with no intention of providing the expected editorial services in return (Beall, 2012; Fazel & Hartse, 2020; Soler & Cooper, 2019). Using qualitative analytical methods and a corpus of 50 unsolicited email messages sent by predatory publishers and collected during the past two years together with their respective websites, this study sets out to investigate the main themes that prevail in predatory publishing to generate interest and convince authors for submitting their work. It also critically assesses deceptive editorial practices that may flout mainstream academic publication standards. These two datasets were iteratively coded and qualitatively analysed by means of NVivo 11 Pro. Target elements as documented in current literature were first identified and then organised into broad themes that were coded into initial nodes and later grouped into related categories, yielding three main themes and sixteen subthemes. Broadly, the findings show that (i) predatory discourse overuses boastful language and relies on self-promotional explicit references to high quality in order to persuade authors; and (ii) indicators (like deceptive bibliometrics or counterfeit titles) act as “hooks” to achieve their predatory aims. Lastly, implications of how predatory journals contribute to the dissemination of non-validated knowledge in academia and their impact on scholars aiming for visibility in academia will also be discussed.

Keywords

academic discourse; fake editorial practices; open access; peer review; predatory journals

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Dialogicity in individual and institutional scientific blogs

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Abstract

The paper discusses the impact of digital affordances on academic discourse and its dialogicity. Starting from the wider context, i.e. the rapid expansion of digital means of communication and the global extension of the participation framework in Web 2.0, I look at the impact it has had on academic discourse on blogs. The focus of the study is on variation across institutional and individual scientific blogs, i.e. blogs that are managed by journals, magazines or associations involved in the dissemination of scientific information and blogs that are managed by individual researchers. Using comparable corpora of blog posts and comments from different areas in science (see Freddi (2020) for a presentation of the corpus), I look in particular at markers of dialogicity from three points of view: the representation of participants (markers of self-reference, reference to the reader and attribution), markers of communicative action (organizational units and patterns), evaluative dialogue (evaluative lexis and dialogic contraction and expansion) (Bondi, 2018). The analysis of keywords and key-phrases (as calculated by Wordsmith Tools 8.0) shows that: a) institutional blogs tend to favour patterns of attribution, while individual blogs tend to favour reference to the direct participants; b) institutional blogs tend to favour metadiscursive references over metacognitive references and c) evaluative dialogue is much more clearly highlighted in individual than institutional blogs. The data confirm the expectation that blogs managed by individual scientists emphasize personal voice and interpersonal elements, while “institutional” blogs are comparatively more informational. Writer voice in institutional blogs may be influenced by the presence of the institution itself as website “principal” (Goffman, 1981), taking responsibility for the web space that hosts the blog, and superimposing less personal forms of authoritativeness. This determines noticeable variation across the blogosphere, even when restricting the focus to “scientific blogs”. The presence of more or less personal forms of voice confirms the prominence of writer identity(/ies) in blogs: web communication often blurs the distinction between expert and non-expert audiences, but it highlights the need to manifest the self of the blog(-ger).

Keywords

individual blogs; institutional blogs; dialogicity; scientific discourse

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“Experts don’t know anything.” The construction of scientific expertise in user-generated content

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Abstract

In the age of social media, distrust of the medical and scientific communities has proliferated, posing a challenge to the authority of major health organisations. While the value of mainstream scientific advances is undermined and public health measures are infringed, alternative theories are being proposed and propagated, receiving massive public attention. The dynamics of this process of epistemological levelling could be observed clearly during the COVID-19 pandemic, when large amounts of false information circulated freely, hindering the (already difficult) task of providing clear information and guidelines to protect public health. One of the salient features of the user generated content in this context was the way that “experts” and “expert knowledge” became a disputed term, being used to legitimise claims made by both mainstream and alternative sources (Salaverría et al., 2020), but also frequently being used to delegitimise others’ claims, with “expert” voices placed in contrast to “common sense” or personal experience, albeit of a second-hand nature (Laurent-Simpson & Lo, 2019; Breeze, 2021).

In this paper, I analyse the construction of experts and expert knowledge in a corpus consisting of over 250,000 words from reader comments on articles about the COVID-19 vaccine published in the *Mail Online* from February to July 2020. Using methodology from corpus-assisted discourse analysis, I explore the framing of “experts” and “expert knowledge” from a quantitative and qualitative perspective. The conclusions add to our understanding of the way “experts” are represented in public discourse (Wagner et al., 2019; Kienhues et al., 2020), but also suggest a link between political developments related to populism and the devaluation of expert knowledge in the public arena (Clarke & Newman, 2017).

Keywords

knowledge dissemination; conspiracy theories; fake news; user generated content; COVID-19

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Video abstracts for increasing researcher visibility

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Abstract

The video abstract has emerged as a new genre of academic interaction over the last decade. It appeared in response to the new opportunities offered by the internet multimodal digital environment to personalize research papers, share complex information visually and thus extend the reach of scientific research.

This paper explores a small specialised corpus of 16 video abstracts in the field of mathematics published online in the *Journal of Number Theory* (Elsevier). The choice of this journal was motivated by the lack of previous research on video abstracts in the field of mathematics as well as by the availability of the video abstracts on the journal's webpage (Elsevier). Adopting a genre analysis (Swales, 1990) and multimodal analysis (Kress, 2013) perspective and drawing on previous research on video abstracts (e.g. Spicer, 2014; Liu, 2019, 2021), this study undertakes to identify the core and optional rhetorical moves of the genre and to suggest a typology of video abstracts according to the interplay between the audio and the video components involved (e.g. slide show, voice over, talking head) and the prominence given to the researcher and the article content. The analysis will also consider the role of (im)personality and direct address to the listener and their impact on the interaction between the researcher(s) and the audience and the promotion of the author and the article content. The rhetorical moves and function of video abstracts will be compared to those of printed abstracts and their relationship will be discussed. The results of this study hope to contribute to a better understanding of the video abstract as a genre and its potential to promote the author's work. This study will also consider why video abstracts are gaining considerably more popularity in the hard than in the soft sciences.

Keywords

video abstract; research paper; genre analysis; multimodal analysis

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Discipline or Medium? A cross-disciplinary analysis of stance and identity in weblogs by law scholars and scientists

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Abstract

In today's connected world, Internet and online media have become the main sources of knowledge dissemination for the lay public, and platforms such as blogs have established themselves as leading tools for public communication of specialised knowledge. As research has shown, their technological affordances make it possible to disseminate the news faster and to a wider audience and enable timely and immediate online discussions on the issues (Luzón, 2013). Over the years, the way in which blogs have been conveying information has had a strong impact on people's understanding of specialised knowledge, and on their attitudes towards the work of the academic community. A growing interest has also been shown in the study of scholarly blogs, paying attention to disciplinary communities (e.g. popular science blogs), or domain-specific blogs (e.g. science, economics, law). This paper contributes to the above-mentioned research direction, by investigating how law scholars and scientists construct their identity while communicating with their scholarly disciplinary community. Drawing from Hyland's (2005) analysis of stance in academic genres, a quantitative study is presented based on a small comparable corpus of blog posts written by law scholars and life sciences scholars. The analysis combines corpus methodology with a discourse analytic approach and identifies linguistic patterns of self-mention and authorial stance (Jaffe, 2009). In particular, stance-marking devices, such as clauses of thinking, speaking or wishing in the first person (*I think*) and adverbials (*As far as I'm concerned, in my view*), are compared with a view to highlighting disciplinary variation and medium-driven tendencies that cut across knowledge fields.

Keywords

law blogs; science blogs; comparable corpus; self-mention; authorial stance

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A meta-scientific digital Chemistry genre: The Bigger Picture

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Emerging digital Chemistry genres i.e. blogs, trade or science magazines, are often deemed as para-scientific as they are published as a separate entity from the primary research journals they referred to (Ashley Rose, 2014; Luzón, 2013; Kaplan and Radin, 2011). However, new digital Chemistry journals have now adopted a more inclusive scope in an attempt to establish more connections to a wider readership without jeopardising the technical content at the expense of the journal. The “Bigger Picture” section in the Chemistry journal Chem is such a new part-genre.

The study examines the rhetorical moves (Swales, 1990) based on in vivo qualitative data analysis of a 20 recent primary research article corpus in Chem and in conjunction with selected lexico-grammatical patterns that seemed more salient in certain moves (Ädel, 2014). It was found that technical content is not overly simplified but presented with an outreach perspective in mind so as to include more researchers. Also, speculative language is another prominent feature in this section, unlike other Chemistry journals and author guidelines that urge for quantitative evaluations instead (Robinson et al., 2008).

Following an organic chemistry analogy of ortho, meta and para non-hydrogen substituents on a hydrocarbon ring indicating their positioning, it seems germane to suggest that this new genre cannot be classed as para-scientific as it is included in the main primary research article after publication and it seems to be tailored to the needs of both discipline-specific and wider scientific community. In this light, the Bigger Picture gives rise to a new type of genre, i.e. ‘meta-scientific’ genre, whose disciplinary scope and part-genre based differences have important implications for EAP writing research and pedagogy (Bhatia, 2006).

Keywords

the Bigger Picture; new genre; moves analysis; research article; chemistry; academic research writing

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Size does matter: Introducing science to the general public in 3-minute talks

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Abstract

In recent times, making science available to the general public has emerged and started consolidating. The growing acceptance of online genres (i.e. parascientific genres) as tools to democratize science and spread scientific research to everyone has become a fact (Luzón & Pérez-Llantada, 2019). Among those new genres, we can find the international scientific talks competition called FameLab (organized worldwide by the British Council, as well as by the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT)). It consists of 3-minute talks in English on scientific and/or technological subjects. Our observation of some of those talks has shown us that showing a positive attitude while delivering a message seems to be an important element in those presentations. Taking into account previous research on engagement, 3-minute talks, and multimodality (Fortanet-Gómez & Ruiz-Madrid, 2016; Luzón, 2019; Vásquez, 2019), we would like to analyse the 2020 FameLab talks since they were not delivered as live events (as in prior editions) but as pre-recorded ones due to the pandemics. This way, the analysis may not depend on the camera shots or on the audience reactions. We would like to look at the combination of verbal (positive messages, use of storytelling) and non-verbal features (use of props, hands movements and smiling face) that may be intended to engage the audience, compelling them to react to the presentation. Discourse cannot be analysed in an isolated way and multimodality plays an important role, not only in engaging the audience in a complex scientific topic but also in combining knowledge and discourse as part of the same event. As ESP practitioners, we hope our research could bring new rhetorical tools to be applied in our teaching, but also the understanding of how science is communicated broadly and how scientists' discursive practices evolve.

Keywords

3-minute talk; multimodality; positivity; audience engagement; science communication

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Research visibility and author ethos: A comparative study of 3MT presentations and research group videos

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Abstract

Over the last two decades, academic research has acquired a strong digital media presence. Research institutes and universities can now disseminate their research output directly to a global, non-specialist audience, bypassing the need for mediators such as science journalists. These developments have however raised several challenges for research institutions: how to communicate esoteric research findings in an environment of context collapse (Marwick & boyd, 2011)? how to train researchers in the new communication skills required? how to negotiate different research identities: professional, disciplinary, institutional, and individual?

To examine how academic research has risen to these challenges, we compare two new digital genres, situated at different stages in researchers' careers: Three Minute Thesis presentations (3MTs) by doctoral students, and Research Group Videos (RGVs) produced by researchers in university laboratories. The 3MT competition, created in 2008, aims to provide novice researchers with early training in the rhetorical dexterity needed to showcase their research to a broad audience (Carter-Thomas & Rowley-Jolivet, 2020), while the recent growth of RGVs reflects the efforts by teams of experienced researchers to gain visibility for their work by promoting it online (Luzón, 2019).

Adopting a discursive, socially constructed view of identity (Flowerdew & Wang, 2015), which involves the selection of both content and linguistic expression to communicate the desired identity, we first carry out a comparative content analysis of the two genres to identify which aspects of research activity the researchers choose to foreground or downplay and the tactics exploited to make the topics accessible, and secondly investigate certain salient linguistic and multimodal features that characterize the researchers' ethos or identities projected. This comparison enables us to address the question of whether seniority or expertise play a role and to what extent the various personalization, interactional and attention-getting devices used vary from one genre and one discipline to another as researchers vie for visibility in an overtly competitive research world.

Our corpus contains 60 video recordings: 30 3MTs and 30 RGVs, half in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) and half in scientific disciplines (STEM). All the videos

are brief "scholarly soundbites", averaging 3 minutes in length (Rowley-Jolivet & Carter-Thomas, 2019).

Keywords

Three Minute Thesis presentations (3MTs); Research Group Videos (RGVs); researcher identities; promotion; recontextualisation

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Utmost hybridity: Promotional trends in technology disclosures

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Abstract

Starting out from the principles of Swales' (1998) textography and by means of netnographic methods (Kozinets, 2015), in this presentation I explore the current promotional trends in the institutional online dissemination of technologies at an emblematic technical university in Spain, the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. I will pay special attention to the new genre constellations allowed by digital media affordances, to the discourse they generate, and to the phenomena of genre borrowing, appropriation and innovation (Bhatia, 2004; Tardy, 2016), as well as to both the intended and actual discourse communities behind the texts. My first-approach focus will be set on the analysis of personalisation, interdiscursivity and promotional strategies in an electronic corpus of 134 disclosures displayed in the English version of the UPM's technologies portfolio. I will point to the extreme hybrid quality of the samples under study as 'borderline' between the advertisement, the scientific abstract and poster, and the journalistic news reporting and interview. Finally, I will reflect on their possible repercussions on the audience and the future of the genre, as well as make the case for explicit training of licensing staff, inventors/scientists and students in sci-tech communication with lay and mixed audiences, together with a close collaboration between the Offices of Technology Transfer (OTTs) and applied linguistics departments.

Keywords

technology disclosures; netnography; hybridity; genre innovation; promotional discourse

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